

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

ANALYSIS AND STUDY OF THE POSSIBLE CAUSES OF THE PRODUCTION ACCIDENT OF AN ELECTRIC ARC FURNACE

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Abstract

The construction features of electric arc furnaces (EAF) and the processes in them in steel production were studied using available materials and the Internet. A failed electric arc furnace was investigated and studied. It was found that the requirements for production and steel casting were met when charging and putting the furnace into operation. The technology for producing steel in a situation of the first melt after a long downtime was met. In all likelihood, the production accident with EAF occurred as a result of an unforeseen event or as a result of circumstances that could not be noticed, detected and prevented during the production process.

Keywords: electric arc furnace, steel casting, production accident

1. Introduction

1.1. Steel production in electric arc furnaces

When producing steel in electric furnaces, the heat necessary to carry out metallurgical processes is obtained from the electrical energy used. Therefore, the processed material does not change its composition under the influence of the fuel. Electric furnaces have a number of advantages compared to conventional furnaces: the ability to produce steel with a lower sulfur content, as well as much better deoxidation; the content of non-metallic inclusions can be minimized and minimal combustion of alloying elements can be achieved; they allow rapid heating to high temperatures and the creation of an oxidizing or reducing atmosphere. This makes electric furnaces particularly reliable for producing high-quality carbon and alloy steels. The electric arc furnace is a cylindrical vessel made of steel sheet. The floor and walls are lined with acidic or basic refractory material, and the vault is built with refractory bricks. In larger furnaces, the vault is movable. Usually, graphite electrodes are lowered through three holes in the arch, which are secured so that they can move vertically with special mechanisms. The furnace is most often filled through a door located opposite the opening for discharging the finished steel. In larger furnaces, the filling is done through the movable arch. To discharge the slag and steel casting, the whole furnace with the electrodes can be tilted using a hydraulic drive. The starting materials for producing steel in an electric arc furnace are secondary ferrous metals. The composition of the starting materials determines the nature of the process. When the starting materials contain a significant amount of harmful impurities, the so-called "production of steel with complete oxidation of the impurities" is carried out. When the content of harmful impurities is within the permissible limits, the so-called "production of steel with partial oxidation of the impurities" is carried out. The nature of the cladding of the

EAF also depends on the purity of the starting materials. Most often, electric arc furnaces are of a cladding-based nature [1,2].

1.2 Technological and technical features of electric arc furnace No. 3

To improve the efficiency of the EDF, the following technical solutions have been adopted and implemented: cooling of the roof (except for the small central roof made of refractory material); cooling of the shell walls using water-cooled panels with forced circulation (closed circuit); automatic regulation of the electrodes with a high reaction speed to maintain constant electrode current and arc voltage (optimal values); correct electrode circuit, such as to allow uniform melting of the scrap and at the same time to reduce the effect of electric arc radiation on the panels and the shell refractory; eccentric bottom casting system (EBT); casting of the melt without slag, with minimal receptivity to non-metallic elements (O_2 , N_2 , H_2) and minimal temperature losses; fifth hole for charging furnace additives; installation of the shell, intended to optimize the accessible volume and minimize the temperature unevenness of the liquid steel, in order to reduce the thermal load on the refractory lining; installation of the external panels. The implemented technical solutions allow for the optimization of working practices with a significant reduction in: the time between castings; electricity consumption; electrode wear; refractory lining wear; furnace maintenance times; manual interventions by operators. Moreover, they allow for making melting and casting operations safer; improving the quality of the production; retaining slag inside the shell, thus making the subsequent refining of the steel inside the ladle easier. EDP No. 3 is equipped with modules that allow for the injection of oxygen into the metal bath. Technological features include:

- "liquid mirror" practice. The maximum capacity of the furnace allows the practice of liquid mirror, which consists of retaining inside the furnace a quantity of molten steel of about 10% of the weight of the scrap

charge. The liquid steel that remains in the furnace allows faster melting due to the better productivity of the burners and the oxygen tube. Consequently, the electrodes can “penetrate” the scrap quickly with “long arcs”, thus allowing not only a reduction in melting time, but also a reduction in electrode wear and better arc stability during the open melting phases, which are the most critical for the operation.

-foamed slag: it covers the electric arc to protect the cooled panels and the refractory lining of the shell from the heat emitted by the arc; moreover, it reduces noise, increases electricity production and reduces vibrations from the electrode holder arms, effectively transmitting the energy to the arc and improving metal yield.

-high impedance operation: long arc furnace operation and high impedance are advantageous as they result in low electrical losses and high arc stability; reduce power supply disturbances; reduce mechanical stress.

-stirring of the metal bath is used to homogenize the temperature of the steel and to analyze the quality of the steel, thus favoring the thermal exchange between the slag and the steel and improving the diffusion of additives in the metal bath.

1.3. Construction features

EDF No. 3 has a cooled roof. The roof is made of a tubular support structure with a set of steel panels suspended from it. In the central part there is a hole to accommodate the refractory roof with holes for the electrodes. In the small roof there is an additional hole for charging alloying additives and calcium salts. The small roof is completely independent of the roof and can be easily removed and replaced. Diametrically opposite to the lifting system, the roof includes an oval hole for connecting a smoke extraction elbow made up of water-cooled pipes. Such a system allows the roof to be cooled without a large refractory coating. The EDF also has a device for lifting the electrodes. The system is made up of electrodes consisting of a steel structure with guides welded to it; these guides slide on 4 pairs of guide wheels assembled on supports that are tightened to the supporting body.

The EDF has a modular DANARC system. The requirement for low electrical energy consumption requires additional chemical energy. The chemical energy supply as gas and carbon combusted with oxygen can be controlled for the best possible use of the energy content in the reaction products. The DANARC modules represent the latest development in chemical energy supply. The system is designed to inject oxygen, carbon and fuel to obtain a highly efficient contribution to the melting. The DANARC module consists of a double injector block (the injector blocks do not have to be adjacent) which operates fixed to the side wall of the furnace. The two types of injectors are called Oxygenjet (oxygen nozzle) and Carbojet (carbon nozzle). The Oxygenjet is a water-cooled injector of oxygen and natural gas. It has two operating modes as a burner and as an oxygen supply tube. The Carbonjet is a water-cooled injector of oxygen, natural gas and carbon. It has two operating modes as a burner and as a carbon supply tube. The EDF uses UHP graphite electrodes. Graphite electrodes have the physical, chemical and electrical

properties necessary for melting steel, since the arc in the preheating furnace is a significant source of heat. The characteristics of the electrodes must correspond with the technical specifications of the DANIELI company.

Cooling system. Water is mainly used as the cooling fluid during the controlled cooling of the furnace components that are subjected to thermal radiation. This is the reason why special attention was paid to the design and construction of the cooling system. The system is closed-circuit, except for the free cooling system of the electrodes; it is fed with clean and filtered industrial water coming from the water purification system and supplies the circuits of the furnace components that need to be cooled according to a certain diagram. If water is missing (when the pumping station is damaged or there is no power supply), the circuits (especially in the power supply unit for the roof structure) are supplied by emergency water coming from an elevated gravimetric tank with pressure and minimum flow rate to protect people or equipment from damage [2,3].

2. Technological process of production and pouring in EDF No. 3

The electric arc furnace works with secondary ferrous metals raw material, which is called scrap. Secondary ferrous metals (scrap) are received in the scrap yard by rail cars or trucks. Secondary ferrous metals are supplied by certified companies authorized to purchase and deliver scrap. Companies supplying scrap deliver the scrap to the secondary ferrous metals workshop accompanied by the relevant documents: certificate of origin, type of scrap: alloyed scrap, secondary ferrous metals. Secondary ferrous metals are from the Republic of Bulgaria and imported from abroad. A system has been introduced according to which secondary ferrous metals are classified according to 16 quality indicators. The most important of them are the presence of non-ferrous metals, the presence of non-metallic components, the presence of closed containers (under pressure), radiation control. Scrap is received from the scrap yard pre-sorted. The quality of the secondary ferrous metals is determined during sorting. According to the quality and size, they are distributed to the appropriate sorting field. In order to be fed to the furnace, the scrap is loaded into steel baskets, called bins. In the sorting workshop, the baskets are loaded by filling them with the help of magnets and grabs mounted on the cranes. After filling and weighing each basket, it is transported with a heavy-duty conveyor called a bin truck. Using a 180-ton crane, the scrap from the baskets is poured into the furnace, the vault of which is previously opened. After closing the furnace vault, the operator gives a command to close the furnace switch. The electrodes remain under voltage. The process of melting the secondary ferrous metals (melt) begins. The melting process is also combined with oxidative refining processes. Usually, the furnace is loaded with three or four baskets depending on the density of the scrap. Consecutively, after melting the first basket, the second one is placed; after melting the second-third, etc. After melting the last basket, heating of the metal bath to a temperature of 1600-1650°C follows (begins). The duration of one melt is 70-75 minutes. After reaching the required temperature and the desired carbon content,

the melt is poured into a steel bucket. Then the process of out-of-furnace treatment begins. Together with the secondary ferrous metals, slag-forming materials - lime, magnesite and carburizers - are fed into the furnace. Anthracite, 1-3 mm in size, is also injected to foam the slag. The process is intensified with the help of oxygen gas, fed through the relevant modules of the furnace.

EDP No. 3 has an automated dual control system. There are manual control elements on the Main Control Panel: functional keyboards: for control/drive of the electrodes; for control/drive of the roof; for general electrical control; for control/drive of the slag door and movement of the furnace and control of the cooling system. There are control elements on the Local Control Panel: enabling/disabling local control elements; EBT movement control system; weight control; manual control elements for tilting the furnace and visualizing the tilted position; control/drive of the gas injection process; general emergency button. There is a system for automatic adjustment of the electrodes for operation: the automatic combined movement of the electrodes (raising/lowering) is performed by pressing the corresponding button on the Main Control Panel. The movement of the electrodes depends on the position of the roof and is controlled by an automatic system before

opening the roof and after closing it. The automatic operation of the electrodes (raising/lowering) is controlled by the furnace regulator when the electrodes are released; the furnace electrical switch is closed; the automatic operation is controlled only by the Main Panel; the type of regulation is selected by the operator via the corresponding button on the Main Panel selector [2,3,4].

3. Probable causes of the production accident at EDP No. 3

After analysis of the technical documentation and on-site inspection, it was established that the nature of the “explosion” with predominantly slag ejection and a minimal amount of metal indicates that the process (accident) was caused “from above”, and did not develop in the molten metal with a subsequent explosion. This is also confirmed by the main damage to the furnace we have identified: damage to the furnace vault lifting mechanism; damage to the furnace vault: knocked out panels, thrown out refractory bricks; damage to the small vault (delta section); damaged electrode holders; damaged elbow for air extraction from the furnace; - damaged main masonry on the eastern side of the furnace (the spare is in place); disconnected water connections.

Figures 1-4 present photographs of some of the more serious damage to the furnace.

Figures 1÷4. Major damages identified in the EDP

At the preliminary investigation stage, we identified the following possible (probable) causes of the production accident subject to analyzes:

1. Failure to perform the intended technological operations before starting the furnace.
2. Condition and type of the supplied secondary ferrous metals (scrap); presence of closed containers,

such as gas cylinders, which can cause explosive reactions.

3. Violation of the production technology.
4. Unforeseen leakage of water from the water-cooled panels of the furnace behind the refractory masonry.

5. Explosion inside the electric furnace, mainly due to water (even in small quantities) in the charged scrap, which starts some explosive chemical-physical reactions, or to micro-leaks in the cooling system of the roof or shell, which are more frequent and insidious, despite the optimal quality of the cooled panels. These leaks, even the smallest ones, can be recognized during scrap charging in the form of spatters either by the color of the scrap or by the arrangement in the furnace, since in case of leaks it sticks to the furnace wall affected by the water leak and becomes dark instead of red-orange. Scrap accumulated around this area will collapse into the metal bath after an explosive exothermic reaction due to the significant gas evolution together with the sudden evaporation of the water that wetted the scrap. We have detected splashes of liquid metal on the water-cooled panels, but these could also be the result of the explosion.

6. Unpredictable tilting of the furnace forward (pouring side) with the EBT closed. As a result, the explosions. As a result, the molten steel in the EBT area would reach dangerous levels and come into contact with the cooled shell panels, with the risk of serious explosions.

7. Unpredictable breakage and collapse of one or more electrodes in the shell. Usually the breakage occurs at the electrode joints. It is necessary to strictly follow the instructions for preparing the electrodes, performing qualified procedures for transferring and joining the electrode columns, preparing the joints, placing the connecting nipple, preparing the electrode elements.

8. Chemical-physical reactions in the liquid steel. Some physico-chemical reactions in the liquid steel inside the shell can develop and cause explosions or overflow of the liquid steel from the furnace. They can be due to oxidation reactions in the bath or to sudden collapse of scrap from the furnace walls. However, the reaction starts slowly and can be avoided.

9. Unpredictable water leakage from the water-cooled panels of the large furnace arch.

4. Conclusion

After studying and analyzing the available technical documentation and inspecting the EDP No. 3 in the condition immediately after the accident and after the dismantling of the furnace, we found that the requirements for production and steel casting were met when loading and putting the furnace into operation. The technology for producing steel in a situation of the first melt after a long downtime was met. Factors 3.5, 3.7 and 3.9 remain as possible (probable) causes of the production accident with EDP No. 3. We have not established any culpable behavior of an official who did not comply with the technology of the production and metal casting process, as a result of which the production accident with EDP No. 3 occurred, which is causally related to the accident that occurred. In our opinion, in all likelihood, the production accident with EDP No. 3 occurred as a result of an unpredictable (unforeseeable) event or as a result of circumstances that could not be noticed, detected and prevented during the production process, i.e. f. in all likelihood a random event occurred.

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